

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE NECESSITY OF USING NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATIVE MEANS TO OPTIMIZE THE LEARNING PROCESS

Khudiyeva Farida Tofiq

*PhD in Pedagogy, Associate Professor
Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University, Azerbaijan*

Abstract

People do not always use verbal means of communication in the process of communication. Often, they use non-verbal means in addition to verbal speech to reinforce the information they convey verbally or to express their feelings, thoughts, desires, and moods. One of the researchers, Albert Meyerabian, has determined that people receive information through verbal means less than through non-verbal means. The French psychologist François Sulje, who holds the same opinion, shows that, in numerical terms, words have an impact of 7% in the communication process, various sounds, tone of voice, intonation of 38%, and other non-verbal means, facial expressions and gestures of 55%. This means that non-verbal means play a more important role in our communication than verbal means.

Keywords: communication, innovations, teaching, training, education

Non-verbal means of communication are divided into several parts:

1. Extralinguistics (“extra” - outside, “lingua” - language) are sound ways of transmitting emotions outside of language, speech. This includes non-verbal means such as moaning, sighing, crying, laughing, coughing, etc.

2. Prosody - the expression of what is said by sound. These are intonation, timbre, pause, loudness of voice, etc. With the help of these means, one can determine the emotional state of a person during a conversation, his attitude to the interlocutor and the subject of discussion.

3. Kinesics - are movements that complement what is said. This includes expressive facial movements (facial expressions, gaze, eye contact and eye movements) and body movements (gestures, posture).

4. Takesika- studies the touch used in communication. These are handshakes, clapping, hugging, kissing and caressing.

5. Proxemics- (eng. - proximity, orientation, distance) determines the orientation of partners when communicating, the distance between people. The founder of proxemics, Edward Hall, called it spatial psychology.

Proxemics identifies the following distance zones:

1. Intimate zone (15-45 cm) - this is the zone of communication between parents and children, spouses, close friends and relatives. People allow only those with whom they are emotionally attached to enter this area.

2. Personal zone (46 cm-1.2 m.) - this distance is the distance between us and others around the tea table, at parties organized with colleagues, at gatherings with friends.

3. Social zone (1.2-3.6 m) - this distance is used in communication with strangers: a seller, a repairman who came to our house for repairs, a worker who has just started working, etc.

4. Public zone (over 400 cm) - the distance of communication among the crowd, in the audience.

Let's get acquainted with other non-verbal means of communication that play a role in the communication process:

Body language (facial expressions and gestures). When we say body language, we mean facial expressions and gestures. It is impossible to imagine communication without facial expressions and gestures. They are punctuation marks of oral speech. Just as punctuation marks in writing help to understand the idea, facial expressions and gestures serve the same purpose in oral speech.

“Mimicry” is a Greek word and means imitation. The meaningful movement of the speaker's facial muscles is called mimicry. That is, mimicry is messages given through facial movements (eyes, eyebrows, forehead, mouth, lips). Facial expressions and facial movements are the main indicators of human feelings. Some scientists note that there are 6 types of facial expressions:

1. joy, happiness; 2. surprise; 3. fear; 4. anger; 5. hatred; 6. indifference.

Facial expressions make the spoken word more expressive, and at the same time can change the meaning of the word. For example:

raised eyebrows, wide-open eyes, half-open mouth - surprise;

furrowed eyebrows, wrinkled forehead, narrowed eyes, closed lips, clenched teeth - anger;

shining eyes, raised edges of lips, the appearance of a smile on the face - indicate joy, happiness.

The most expressive feature of the face is reflected in the eyes. There is such a proverb, “the eyes are the mirror of the soul”. Indeed, sometimes one look of a person replaces a thousand words. The eyes create the conditions for communication. With their gaze, the speaker shows their sincerity, confidence in their position, and trust, as if building a bridge to the heart of the interlocutor. It is possible to understand the attitude of our interlocutor towards us, his sincerity, whether he is listening to the conversation or not by looking at his eyes. Looking into the eyes of the interlocutor while talking not only expresses our interest in him, but also

allows us to understand what he wants to tell us. If our interlocutor feels our gaze, he will listen to us more carefully, smile to express his approval, and in the end, his likelihood of liking both us and our speech will increase. In general, eye contact, gaze, is the main means of understanding between the speaker and the listener in the art of oratory and is considered the beginning of a successful speech.

Mimics are not always understood and interpreted in a uniform, identical way. Different cultural People with different levels of intelligence and social development perceive these in different ways. For example, the Japanese do not look each other in the eye when talking, this is considered uncivilized. In our case, during a business conversation or negotiation, they look each other in the eye for confidence and to establish a good relationship. If the interlocutor looks away or looks at the ground, this creates distrust in the other party.

Everyone who is talking to the other party should be able to “understand” and “read” the facial expressions of the interlocutor. At the same time, they should know how much they can control their facial expressions and how expressive they are. In this regard, everyone should try to study their facial expressions, monitor the movements of the eyebrows, forehead, lips. In order for facial expressions to be expressive, it is sometimes necessary to practice in front of a mirror. For this, it is necessary to pronounce expressions of different emotions (funny, cheerful, sad, tragic, etc.). At this time, it is determined whether the facial expression corresponds to the emotion. Experienced speakers and actors skillfully use this method. Gestures. The hand and arm movements made by the speaker during a speech are called gestures. Gestures are messages given using the entire body (hands, arms, fingers, head, feet). These features that distinguish a person from other living beings help him express his feelings and thoughts, joy and sadness, and emphasize important moments. The gestures used by each person are formed according to his character. Gestures make speech more interesting, clarify it, and create conditions for better perception of speech. Each gesture made in place increases the impact of speech, attracts the attention of the listener more.

Remember that in a changing world, new types of skills are needed.

- The goal of modern education is to teach creative approaches, ways to develop critical thinking, rather than imparting knowledge. Schools of the future should help students to be more effective in their judgment, critical and creative thinking, and in their personal and social activities.

- The overall success in education cannot be greater than the success of the teacher. The better the teachers, the better the education system. The most important thing is to encourage the most talented people to become teachers. The most talented teachers should be sent to the most difficult, remote regions. China does this very well.

- Teachers should be given more opportunities to observe their colleagues, special attention should be paid to the formation of team spirit in teaching, and the skills of students to work in teams.

- Good teachers are researchers, they do not just teach what is written in the textbook. For example, teachers in Shanghai teach fewer lessons. Because they spend most of their time developing new teaching technologies.

- In the future, teachers will focus more on using interdisciplinary integration.

- In times of uncertainty, students need to be able to find their own way. For this, the education provided should act as a compass in their lives.

- If you push students to memorize a new formula every day, they will get bored with the lesson. You need to instill in them the mindset of that subject. Take mathematics for example. Instead of memorizing formulas, you need to instill in them a mathematical mindset. Understanding the cause and essence of the problem is more important than memorizing formulas.

- You must have a clear vision of what values you will form in students. Because the future of education is social values. Being open, respecting different cultures, courage, and curiosity are key.

- Literacy is no longer about finding information, but about creating knowledge. Instead of teaching the results of an experiment, it is more effective to prepare an experiment with students.

- The importance of reading literacy is increasing more and more. When you ask a question on Google today, you are faced with hundreds of answers. No one tells you which one is correct. Therefore, developing reading literacy and critical thinking skills is of particular importance.

- You need to build a system that will allow all students to discover their potential.

- The main focus in education should always be on development. How do students learn better, how do teachers teach better, how do schools improve?

- The ability to use knowledge creatively should be developed. One should strive to be good at creativity, not at memorization.

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